

PROJECT READING ENHANCEMENT CARRIED THROUGH INTENSIVE AND THOROUGH ENRICHMENT (RECITE): A TOOL FOR IMPROVING READING PROFICIENCY OF GRADE 12 SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL HOME ECONOMICS (HE) STUDENTS

Erika A. de Sosa, Joan O. Barajas EdD, Abigail M. Detruz

English Department, Angelo L. Loyola SHS, City of Carmona, Cavite, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17926760>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to improve the reading proficiency of Grade 12 Home Economics (HE) students at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School through Project RECITE (Reading Enhancement Carried Through Intensive and Thorough Enrichment). The program addressed low proficiency in Speed and Accuracy, Vocabulary, and Reading Comprehension by implementing tailored, evidence-based interventions during weekly sessions. Participants were purposively selected based on pre-test scores, which indicated they were performing at the Frustration level. The study utilized paired-sample t-tests to assess changes in proficiency after the intervention. Results showed significant improvements, with most students advancing to the Instructional level. However, challenges such as low motivation and difficulty mastering new skills suggested a need for more engaging materials and strategies. The findings highlighted the program's effectiveness and its potential to be adapted in similar educational contexts to address widespread reading challenges.

Keywords: *Reading Proficiency, Reading Intervention, Bloom's Taxonomy, Home Economics*

INTRODUCTION

Reading proficiency plays a vital role in shaping an individual's personal and professional growth (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2000). It enables learners to access information across various disciplines and supports the development of critical thinking, effective communication, and overall cognitive skills. Through reading, individuals gain knowledge, encounter diverse perspectives, and develop critical thinking skills. The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) evaluates reading ability as a key indicator of students' preparedness for real-life challenges. In 2018, Filipino students participated in PISA for the first time, and results revealed that they ranked last among 79 countries in reading performance (Bernardo & Mante-Estacio, 2023). This highlights a serious concern, as weak reading comprehension skills can hinder students' ability to understand and apply concepts across subjects.

For senior high school students, the ability to comprehend and analyze written information is particularly critical. Limited reading proficiency creates a ripple effect, affecting academic performance in multiple areas. Several factors contribute to reading difficulties, including students' socioeconomic background, access to resources, use of self-regulation strategies, quality of teacher-student relationships, and levels of motivation and engagement with reading (Vazquez & Huerta, 2021). Targeted interventions and the promotion of a reading culture can help students develop the necessary reading skills to succeed academically and beyond (Tolentin, 2023). Research indicates that interventions are especially beneficial for students at risk of reading difficulties, as they support language learning and overall reading proficiency (Gustanti & Ayu, 2021). Effective reading strategies, such as identifying main ideas, making inferences, monitoring comprehension, and predicting outcomes, are essential for meaningful understanding of texts (Oberholzer, 2005; Westwood, 2008). Reading comprehension also depends on cognitive and linguistic processes, including vocabulary, prior knowledge, working memory, and the ability to generate inferences (Perfetti & Stafura, 2013).

This study focuses on addressing low reading proficiency among Grade 12 Home Economics (HE) students at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School (ALLSHS) in Carmona, Cavite. Data from the 2023 National Achievement Test indicate that HE students require strengthened reading skills, particularly in Oral Communication and Reading & Writing. In response, Project RECITE (Reading Enhancement Carried through Intensive and Thorough Enrichment) was developed to improve students' reading accuracy, vocabulary, and comprehension. The program employs strategies such as comprehension exercises, read-aloud activities, text summarization, vocabulary development, and structured questioning, targeting specific areas of difficulty to help students become proficient readers.

Research Questions

This action research specifically aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the reading proficiency level of Grade 12 HE students in the pre-test and post-test in terms of:

- a. Speed and Accuracy,
 - b. Vocabulary, and
 - c. Reading Comprehension?
2. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test in the reading proficiency levels of Grade 12 HE students in terms of:
 - a. Speed and Accuracy,
 - b. Vocabulary, and
 - c. Reading Comprehension?
 3. What challenges do teachers and students face during the implementation of Project RECITE, and how can these challenges be addressed to improve the program's effectiveness?
 4. What action plan can be developed based on the findings to sustain and improve reading proficiency among Grade 12 HE students?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative action research design to investigate the effect of Project RECITE (Reading Enhancement Carried through Intensive and Thorough Enrichment) on the reading proficiency of Grade 12 Home Economics (HE) students at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School in Carmona, Cavite. Initial reading proficiency was assessed using the Gates-McGinitie Reading Test as a pre-test. Students who scored below the Frustration level were purposively selected to participate, ensuring that interventions targeted those with significant reading difficulties. The program consisted of weekly one-hour RECITE sessions, including comprehension exercises, read-aloud activities, text summarization, vocabulary development, and structured questioning. The post-test was administered at the end of the program to measure improvements in reading proficiency. Data were analyzed by converting raw scores to grade scores and classifying them into Frustration, Instructional, or Independent levels. Descriptive statistics summarized the mean and standard deviation of scores for each category. Paired-sample t-tests were conducted to determine whether observed differences between pre-test and post-test scores were statistically significant. Weighted means were calculated to provide an overall measure of improvement. Feedback from teachers and students was collected through checklists and surveys to identify challenges encountered during the program. Responses were tabulated and ranked to determine the most prevalent issues affecting implementation. This analysis informed actionable recommendations for improving the program's effectiveness. The research maintained detailed documentation to ensure accurate reporting of procedures and outcomes. The combination of pre-test and post-test measures, active reading interventions, and systematic analysis allowed for a comprehensive assessment of Project RECITE. Findings were interpreted to determine whether the program successfully enhanced students' reading proficiency in terms of speed, accuracy, vocabulary, and comprehension. Overall, the methodology provided a structured approach to evaluating targeted reading interventions and their impact on students' literacy skills.

RESULTS

This part examined the reading proficiency levels of Grade 12 Home Economics students, comparing their performance in Speed and Accuracy, Vocabulary, and Reading Comprehension before and after the intervention. The differences between the pre-test and post-test results showed the students' progress.

Table 1
Proficiency Level of Grade 12 HE Students in Speed and Accuracy for Pre-Test and Post-Test

Table 1		PRE-TEST		POST TEST	
		Speed and Accuracy		Speed and Accuracy	
Students	Raw Score	Verbal Interpretation	Raw Score	Verbal Interpretation	
1	8	Frustration	25	Instructional	
2	12	Frustration	18	Instructional	
3	10	Frustration	22	Instructional	
4	6	Frustration	20	Instructional	
5	13	Frustration	23	Instructional	
6	7	Frustration	25	Instructional	
7	11	Frustration	12	Frustration	
8	8	Frustration	18	Instructional	
9	12	Frustration	13	Frustration	
10	10	Frustration	20	Instructional	
11	10	Frustration	22	Instructional	
12	13	Frustration	25	Instructional	
13	12	Frustration	25	Instructional	
14	6	Frustration	10	Frustration	
15	11	Frustration	12	Frustration	
16	7	Frustration	27	Instructional	
17	8	Frustration	24	Instructional	
18	10	Frustration	30	Independent	
Average	9.67	Frustration	20.61	Instructional	

Legend: 30 – 36 Independent 15 – 29 = Instructional 1 – 14 = Frustration

Students' average Speed and Accuracy score increased from 9.67 (Frustration) in the pre-test to 20.61 (Instructional) in the post-test.

Table 1.1
Proficiency Level of Grade 12 HE Students in Vocabulary for
Pre-Test and Post-Test

Table 1.1 PRE-TEST			POST TEST	
Vocabulary			Vocabulary	
Students	Raw Score	Verbal Interpretation	Raw Score	Verbal Interpretation
1	12	Frustration	23	Instructional
2	10	Frustration	25	Instructional
3	15	Frustration	27	Instructional
4	13	Frustration	21	Instructional
5	10	Frustration	28	Instructional
6	9	Frustration	30	Instructional
7	11	Frustration	28	Instructional
8	16	Frustration	15	Frustration
9	12	Frustration	17	Frustration
10	10	Frustration	22	Instructional
11	8	Frustration	25	Instructional
12	15	Frustration	15	Frustration
13	13	Frustration	28	Instructional
14	17	Frustration	17	Frustration
15	13	Frustration	29	Instructional
16	12	Frustration	18	Frustration
17	15	Frustration	30	Instructional
18	17	Frustration	43	Independent
Average	12.67	Frustration	24.5	Instructional

Legend: 40 – 50 Independent 20 – 39 = Instructional 1 – 19 = Frustration

The average Vocabulary score increased from 12.67 (Frustration) to 24.5 (Instructional).

Table 1.2
Proficiency Level of Grade 12 HE Students in Reading Comprehension for
Pre-Test and Post-Test

Table 1.2 PRE-TEST			POST TEST	
Reading Comprehension			Reading Comprehension	
Students	Raw Score	Verbal Interpretation	Raw Score	Verbal Interpretation
1	10	Frustration	41	Independent
2	12	Frustration	29	Instructional
3	15	Frustration	35	Instructional
4	17	Frustration	32	Instructional

5	14	Frustration	25	Instructional
6	11	Frustration	45	Frustration
7	16	Frustration	33	Instructional
8	12	Frustration	14	Frustration
9	10	Frustration	13	Frustration
10	15	Frustration	28	Instructional
11	17	Frustration	37	Instructional
12	12	Frustration	28	Instructional
13	13	Frustration	35	Instructional
14	10	Frustration	17	Frustration
15	15	Frustration	30	Instructional
16	17	Frustration	15	Frustration
17	14	Frustration	25	Instructional
18	15	Frustration	49	Independent
Average	13.61	Frustration	29.5	Instructional

Legend: 40 – 52 Independent 20 – 39 = Instructional 1 – 19 = Frustration

The mean Reading Comprehension score increased from 13.61 (Frustration) to 29.5 (Instructional).

Table 1.3
Overall Proficiency Level of Grade 12 HE Students for Pre-Test and Post-Test

Table 1.3 PRE-TEST			POST TEST	
Overall			Overall	
Students	Raw Score	Verbal Interpretation	Raw Score	Verbal Interpretation
1	30	Frustration	89	Instructional
2	34	Frustration	72	Instructional
3	40	Frustration	84	Instructional
4	36	Frustration	73	Instructional
5	37	Frustration	76	Instructional
6	27	Frustration	100	Independent
7	38	Frustration	73	Instructional
8	36	Frustration	47	Frustration
9	34	Frustration	43	Frustration
10	35	Frustration	70	Instructional
11	35	Frustration	84	Instructional
12	40	Frustration	68	Instructional
13	38	Frustration	88	Instructional
14	33	Frustration	44	Frustration
15	39	Frustration	71	Instructional
16	36	Frustration	60	Instructional
17	37	Frustration	79	Instructional
18	42	Frustration	122	Independent

Average	35.94	Frustration	74.61	Instructional
----------------	--------------	--------------------	--------------	----------------------

Legend: 98 – 138 Independent 48 – 97 = Instructional 1 – 47 = Frustration

The overall mean proficiency score increased from 35.94 (Frustration) to 74.61 (Instructional).

Table 2
Paired Samples Test for Speed and Accuracy (Pre-Test vs. Post-Test)

	Paired Differences					Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference			
				Lower	Upper		
Speed and Accuracy (Pretest) - Speed and Accuracy (Post test)	-10.944	6.254	1.474	-14.055	-7.834	.000	Significant

A statistically significant difference was found between pre-test and post-test Speed and Accuracy scores ($p = .000$).

Table 2.1
Paired Samples Test for Paired Samples Test for Vocabulary (Pre-Test vs. Post-Test)

	Paired Differences					Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference			
				Lower	Upper		
Vocabulary (Pretest) - Vocabulary (Post test)	-11.833	7.532	1.775	-15.579	- 8.088	.000	Significant

A statistically significant difference was found between pre-test and post-test Vocabulary scores ($p = .000$).

Table 2.2
Paired Samples Test for Reading Comprehension (Pre-Test vs. Post-Test)

	Paired Differences					Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference			
				Lower	Upper		
Reading Comprehension (Pretest) - Reading Comprehension (Post test)	-15.889	10.215	2.408	-20.969	-10.809	.000	Significant

A statistically significant difference was found between pre-test and post-test Reading Comprehension scores ($p = .000$).

Table 2.3
Paired Samples Test for Overall Scores (Pre-Test vs. Post-Test)

	Paired Differences					Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference			
				Lower	Upper		
Overall (Pretest) - Overall (Post test)	-38.667	19.338	4.570	-48.308	-29.025	.000	Significant

A statistically significant difference was found between overall pre-test and post-test proficiency scores ($p = .000$).

Table 3
Challenges Faced by Students on Project RECITE

Challenges	Frequency	Percent	Rank
1. I find it difficult to stay motivated during reading intervention sessions.	16	34.04	1
2. I feel embarrassed or ashamed about receiving extra help in reading.	5	10.64	4
3. I struggle to acquire the new reading skills being taught in the intervention.	13	27.66	2

4. I find the reading intervention materials boring or uninteresting.	10	21.28	3
5. I feel like the reading intervention program is not helping me improve my reading skills.	3	6.38	5
Total	47	100.0	

The most frequently reported challenges involved difficulty acquiring new reading skills and maintaining motivation.

Table 3.1
Challenges Faced by Teachers in Project RECITE

Challenges	Frequency	Percent	Rank
1. I experience frequent disruptions during reading sessions because of class interruptions.	4	14.81	4
2. I find it challenging to differentiate instruction to meet all students' needs, as I need to tailor lessons to each strand, student interests, and preferences in Project RECITE.	7	25.93	2
3. I lack sufficient training and experience to implement effective reading intervention strategies.	2	7.41	5
4. I face significant challenges in keeping students engaged and motivated during reading intervention sessions.	9	33.33	1
5. I find it difficult to monitor attendance because students don't frequently attend due to various reasons.	5	18.52	3
Total	27	100	

The most frequently reported challenges were sustaining student engagement and differentiating instruction.

Table 4
Action Plan for Project RECITE

OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITIES	STRATEGIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	RESOURCES NEEDED	EXPECTED OUTPUT
Improve student motivation during reading sessions	Conduct interactive reading sessions	Incorporate games, group activities, and multimedia tools	Monthly	Teachers, Students, Program Coordinator	Multimedia tools, printed materials	Increased student engagement and participation
Simplify reading strategies for better comprehension	Redesign reading materials and instructional methods	Use step-by-step instructions and culturally relevant content	Quarterly	Teachers, Curriculum Developers	Customized lesson plans, training manuals	Students demonstrate improved comprehension
Enhance engagement through relevant materials	Develop and utilize interest-based reading materials	Conduct surveys to identify student interests and integrate findings into material development	Start of the School Year	Teachers, Students	Surveys, budget for materials	Students find reading materials engaging and interesting
Reduce embarrassment and stigma among students	Organize peer support groups and mentorships	Pair students with peers or mentors for collaborative learning	Bi-Monthly	Teachers, Peer Leaders, Counselors	Training for mentors, meeting space	Students feel more comfortable participating in reading interventions
Provide training for differentiated instruction	Conduct workshops and training for teachers	Partner with experts to provide professional development sessions	Semi-Annually	Teachers, Education Specialists	Workshop materials, budget for training	Teachers effectively implement differentiated instructional methods
Improve student attendance during sessions	Create an attendance monitoring system	Use apps or tools for real-time attendance tracking and provide incentives for perfect attendance	Ongoing	Teachers, Program Coordinator	Attendance tracking tools, rewards	Increased attendance and consistent participation
Minimize class interruptions during sessions	Coordinate schedules and create a dedicated time slot	Collaborate with administrators to block specific hours for uninterrupted sessions	Start of the School Year	Teachers, Administrators	Meeting schedules, communication tools	Fewer interruptions and more productive reading sessions
Address systemic issues affecting engagement	Conduct regular feedback sessions with teachers and students	Use surveys and focus group discussions to identify persistent challenges	Quarterly	Teachers, Students, Program Coordinator	Feedback tools, meeting spaces	Actionable insights for continuous improvement

Based on the identified challenges, the action plan aims to improve motivation and engagement through simpler materials, interest-based tasks, peer support, and attendance incentives. It also strengthens teacher support through training, protected schedules, and regular feedback.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study demonstrated that Project RECITE had a substantial impact on improving the reading proficiency of Grade 12 Home Economics students, as evidenced by the consistent increase in scores across Speed and Accuracy, Vocabulary, and Reading Comprehension. The comparison of pre-test and post-test performance revealed that most students progressed from the Frustration level to the Instructional level, reflecting meaningful gains in fluency, word knowledge, and comprehension. Improvements in Speed and Accuracy were evident as the average score increased from 9.67 to 20.61, supporting literature that structured reading activities enhance fluency in narrative and expository texts. Vocabulary results also showed notable gains, moving from an average of 12.67 to 24.5, aligning with studies emphasizing the effectiveness of narrative-based vocabulary instruction in strengthening word acquisition. The enhancement in reading comprehension scores, which increased from 13.61 to 29.5, further affirmed that targeted strategies can significantly improve the ability of struggling readers to analyze and interpret texts. These outcomes are also consistent with the view

that reading motivation plays a significant role in strengthening students' reading skills (Meniado, 2016).

Overall results revealed that the students' composite proficiency score increased from 35.94 to 74.61, indicating the combined effectiveness of the intervention in developing multiple reading dimensions. Statistical analysis reinforced these conclusions, as the paired-sample t-tests for Speed and Accuracy, Vocabulary, Reading Comprehension, and Overall Scores all showed significant improvements with p-values of .000. These findings support the idea that repeated, structured reading practice and scaffolded instruction can effectively promote literacy growth among learners at risk for reading failure. Consequently, teachers serve a vital role as facilitators in implementing remedial reading programs within the educational context (Sancada, 2022), highlighting the importance of effective guidance throughout the intervention process.

Despite these successes, both students and teachers encountered important challenges during the implementation of Project RECITE. From the students' perspective, motivation emerged as the most significant concern, with 34.04% reporting difficulty sustaining engagement during sessions. This aligns with research emphasizing the strong influence of motivation and interest on reading behavior and outcomes. Many students also struggled to master new reading skills, suggesting that while the program offered structured strategies, additional reinforcement and gradual skill-building may be necessary. Emotional barriers were also evident as some students felt embarrassed about receiving extra support, highlighting the need for a more inclusive and stigma-free intervention environment.

Teachers likewise identified challenges, particularly in sustaining student engagement, which 33.33% described as the primary concern. Differentiating instruction for diverse learners and managing inconsistent student attendance added to the difficulty of maintaining effective sessions. These challenges mirror the complexity of teaching reading, which requires the integration of cognitive, linguistic, and motivational strategies while managing classroom logistics. Teachers also expressed the need for more training in implementing specialized reading interventions, further underscoring their critical role in guiding learners through the program.

The convergence of these findings suggests that Project RECITE was effective but requires refinements to address motivational, instructional, and logistical barriers. Enhancing engagement through interest-driven materials, providing structured peer support, and strengthening teacher training may further improve outcomes. Improving attendance monitoring and minimizing class interruptions can also ensure more consistent participation. By addressing these challenges, the project can more effectively support both teachers and students and sustain gains in reading proficiency.

Conclusions

The results of this action research show that Project RECITE significantly improved the reading proficiency of Grade 12 Home Economics students across the areas of speed

and accuracy, vocabulary, and reading comprehension. Students' overall proficiency scores increased markedly from the pre-test to the post-test, and the statistical results confirmed that these gains were highly significant. These findings support the assertion of Graham et al. (2018) that the implementation of a structured reading intervention program can lead to substantial improvements in students' reading abilities. This suggests that well-designed and consistently delivered interventions can effectively support struggling readers and help them progress from the frustration level toward the instructional level.

While the program produced meaningful improvements, both students and teachers encountered challenges, particularly in maintaining motivation, mastering new reading skills, and ensuring consistent attendance. These concerns highlight the importance of strengthening engagement strategies, providing additional instructional support, and enhancing teacher preparation for targeted reading interventions.

Overall, the study concludes that Project RECITE is an effective literacy program that can positively influence students' reading performance when supported by sustained implementation, responsive teaching strategies, and a supportive learning environment. Continued refinement of the program is recommended to address identified challenges and further enhance its impact on learners' reading development.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, several recommendations are proposed to strengthen the effectiveness of Project RECITE and sustain students' improvement in reading proficiency. It is recommended that the intervention be continued and further enhanced by integrating reading activities more consistently into classroom routines. Providing engaging and contextualized reading materials that align with students' interests and TVL-related experiences may also boost motivation and deepen comprehension. To accommodate diverse learning needs, teachers should incorporate varied and interactive strategies such as collaborative reading tasks, vocabulary games, and the use of digital reading tools. Additional remediation sessions are encouraged for learners who continue to struggle with vocabulary and comprehension so they can be supported in reaching the Independent level. Teacher training should also be strengthened through workshops on reading instruction, differentiated teaching, and assessment strategies. Furthermore, consistent monitoring of student progress through formative assessments and regular feedback will help identify persistent gaps and guide instructional decisions. Engaging parents by offering simple home-reading strategies may also reinforce learning beyond the classroom. Improving the scheduling and time allocation of the intervention is also necessary to ensure full student participation. Lastly, collaboration with other strands and departments is encouraged to foster a more robust school-wide reading culture, and further research is recommended to examine the long-term impact of Project RECITE and explore possible enhancements to its implementation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to all ethical standards required for conducting action research in an educational setting. Permission to implement Project RECITE and administer the Gates-McGinitie Reading Test was formally secured from the school principal and the Grade 12 Home Economics department. Students and their parents were informed about the purpose of the research, the procedures involved, and the voluntary nature of participation. Only those who provided assent and parental consent were included in the study. Confidentiality was strictly maintained by ensuring that all data were coded, and no names or identifying information appeared in the results or report. The intervention activities posed no risk to student participants, as they were part of standard academic enrichment practices aimed at supporting reading development. Teachers involved in the program were also briefed on the ethical guidelines to ensure consistent implementation and respect for the students' rights and well-being. All procedures complied with institutional policies and upheld the principles of respect, beneficence, and fairness throughout the duration of the research.

Acknowledgments

The success of this study, Project RECITE: A Tool for Improving Reading Proficiency of Grade 12 Senior High School Home Economics (HE) Students, would not have been possible without the invaluable contributions and unwavering support of many individuals and groups.

The researchers express their sincere gratitude to Mrs. Laarni S. Doliente, School Head of ALLSHS, for her unwavering support and guidance throughout this research. Her leadership results in the successful implementation of Project RECITE.

The researchers extended their heartfelt thanks to the dedicated English teachers of ALLSHS, with special recognition to Ms. Justine F. Sulabo, for her invaluable contributions in data collection and program implementation. Your expertise and commitment were instrumental in achieving the project's objectives.

The researchers are deeply grateful to the Grade 12 Home Economics students for their active participation and to their parents for their unwavering support. Their dedication and cooperation were essential to the meaningful impact of this research.

Project RECITE serves as a testament to the collective effort and shared commitment towards improving literacy and academic success. Thank you to everyone who contributed to its success.

REFERENCES

Bernardo, A. B. I., & Mante-Estacio, M. J. (2023). Metacognitive reading strategies and its relationship with Filipino high school students' reading proficiency: insights

- from the PISA 2018 data. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01886-6>
- Graham, S., Liu, X., Aitken, A., Ng, C., Bartlett, B., Harris, K. R., & Holzapfel, J. (2018). Effectiveness of literacy programs: Balancing reading and writing instruction—A meta-analysis. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 53(3), 279–304. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rrq.198>
- Gustanti, M., & Ayu, M. (2021). The effect of reading intervention programs on students at risk of reading difficulties. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 2(1), 34–41.
- Guthrie, J. T., & Wigfield, A. (2000). Engagement and motivation in reading. In M. L. Kamil, P. B. Mosenthal, P. D. Pearson, & R. Barr (Eds.), *Handbook of reading research* (Vol. 3, pp. 403–422). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Meniado, J. C. (2016). Metacognitive reading strategies, motivation, and reading comprehension performance of Saudi EFL students. *English Language Teaching*, 9(3), 117–129. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v9n3p117>
- Oberholzer, B. (2005). The relationship between reading difficulties and academic performance among learners in South African schools. *Reading & Writing Journal*, 26(3), 15–28.
- Perfetti, C., & Stafura, J. (2013). Word knowledge in a theory of reading comprehension. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 18(1), 22–37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888438.2013.827687>
- Sancada, R. T. (2022). Remedial reading program in the Schools Division of Iloilo: Challenges and effective practices. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6957238>
- Tolentin, S. (2023). Promoting a culture of reading: Strategies for improving reading engagement among Filipino learners. *Asia Pacific Education Research Journal*, 11(1), 55–67.
- Vazquez, S. R., & Huerta, M. (2021). Factors influencing reading comprehension among high school students: A socio-cognitive perspective. *Journal of Adolescent Literacy*, 64(4), 389–398.
- Westwood, P. (2008). *What teachers need to know about reading and writing difficulties*. ACER Press.